

Impact of Technology on Learning Outcomes and Student Engagement of SS 2 Students in Nassarawa Zonal Education Board of Kano State

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ABSTRACT

The study is titled the impact of technology integration on learning outcomes and student engagement of SS 2 students in Nassarawa zonal education board of Kano state. The study adopted Randomized control trial (RCT) as the research design. The population of the study was estimated at nine thousand eight hundred and sixty-four (9864) SS 2 students from thirty-eight (38) public schools. Fifteen (15) schools were sampled using cluster random sampling technique. Three hundred and seventy (370) were sampled using stratified random sampling technique. One hundred and eighty-five (185) students were assigned to both the control group and experimental groups. The researchers conducted online classes, soft copies of economics notes, personal chats and video calls for the experimental group while the control group only attended their conventional classroom lessons. The result from their terminal examination in economics was to measure the level of student interest and engagement. T-test independent sample was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The findings of the study reveals that there is a significant difference in understanding and retention of complex concepts of those SS 2 students who use digital resources and multimedia materials and those SS 2 students who do not use digital resources and multimedia materials; there is significant difference on the interest and engagement of those SS 2 students who use personalized learning pathways and adaptive technology and those SS2 students who do not use personalized learning pathways and adaptive technology. Based on the findings, recommended among others that parents and guardians should realize the importance of technology integration in determining students learning outcomes and student engagement. Kano state ministry of education should encourage the integration of technology to public secondary schools so as to have a better learning outcomes and student engagement.

Keywords: Technology, Learning outcomes, Student engagement, Randomized control trial

INTRODUCTION

Technology integration is the use of technology resources such as, computers, mobile devices like smartphones and tablets, digital cameras, social media platforms and networks, software applications and internet among others in daily classroom and practices and in the management of school activities. Technology has been confirmed to have great potentials that impact teaching and learning. It motivates and engages students to learn and helps broaden their skills, helps to simulate the workplace experiences thereby, preparing students for the challenges of the labour market. This changes the school environment, facilitates teaching by providing resourceful teaching aids for teachers and connects the school to the outside world. The integration of

technology into classroom offers significant benefits including enhanced learning outcomes, increased student engagement and motivation, improved learning independence and support for student. Learning outcomes are measurable skills, abilities, knowledge or values that students should be able demonstrate as a result of completing a course. It is a measurable statement that describe what students should be able know, do or value by the end of a course or learning experience. Moreover, learning outcomes are statements of knowledge, skills and abilities individual students should possess and can demonstrate upon completion of a learning experience. Learning outcomes are clear statements of what a learner is expected to be able to do, know or value at the completion of a unit of study. Student engagement is a term that describes the level of

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

interest, curiosity and motivation that students show while learning. It also refers to student's willingness to participate and be successful in their learning process. Furthermore, student engagement is a multifaceted concept encompassing components of learning that are cognitive, emotional and behavioural. Student engagement provide immersive, interactive learning experiences that accommodate a variety of learning preferences and styles using technology can increase student engagement. Students can therefore, actively participate in their learning process through multimedia presentations, gamified learning exercises and collaborative online tools. This will in turn increase their motivation, interest and involvement in academic assignments. The importance of technological integration in the educational system cannot be overemphasized with the world changing into a digitalized world. Despite this, schools are still teaching using the traditional approach with pen, papers and chalk. The impact of technology on student's learning outcomes and engagement has repeatedly attracted mixed reaction and opinions. Some argued that using technology leads to over exposure of students to uncontrolled information while some maintained that integration of technology has led to higher levels of engagement and improve learning outcomes. It is believed that the findings and implications of the study will be of a great importance for secondary school administrators, educational practitioners, parents, secondary school students and government. Understanding the impact of technology integration on learning outcomes and student's engagement will enable secondary education institutions and policy makers to develop more strategies and techniques to help students. Furthermore, the findings from this study are expected to expose teachers to novel approach of teaching using integrated technology to enrich their instruction. Moreover, the study will serve as an eye opener for the students to be aware of the importance of technology integration rather than exercising technophobia. This will also enhance their appreciation of mobile phone, laptop, pads. It will also help the students who are preparing for their final examinations which are mostly computer based such as JAMB. Furthermore, Nassarawa and Fagge local government areas of Kano state consist of both public, voluntary and private schools. From the experience of the researchers who resides in Kano, private schools

in the area are increasingly integrating technology into their teaching methods while, public schools are still using conventional methods of teaching and failure of students in examination is a problem of recurring concern in these areas. Thus, the researchers saw the need to integrate technology into the method of teaching instead of using just the conventional method since most of these students are already used to operating smart phones. Lastly, investigation into the impact of technology integration on learning outcomes and student engagement is still ongoing, therefore, there is need for more clarification on the importance of integrating technology on learning outcomes and student engagement. It is against this background that the researchers intend to investigate the impact of technology on learning outcomes and student engagement of students in senior secondary 2 in Nassarawa zonal education board of Kano state.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The objectives of the study include the following:

1. To find out whether the use digital resources and multimedia materials improve understanding and retention of complex concepts of SS 2 students in Nassarawa zonal education board of Kano state.
2. To find out the impact of personalized learning pathways and adaptive technology on interest and engagement of SS 2 students in Nassarawa zonal education board of Kano state.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The following are the research questions:

1. Does the use of digital resources and multimedia materials improve understanding and retention of complex concepts of SS 2 students in Nassarawa zonal education board of Kano state?
2. Does personalized learning pathways and adaptive technology have impact on interest and engagement of SS 2 students in Nassarawa zonal education board of Kano state?

RESEARCH HYPOTHESES

H₀₁: There is no significant difference in the understanding and retention of complex concepts of SS 2 students that use digital resources and multimedia materials and those SS 2 students who do

not use digital resources and multimedia materials in Nassarawa zonal education board of Kano state.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference on the interest and engagement of SS 2 students that use personalized learning pathways and adaptive technology and those SS 2 students who do not use personalized learning pathways and adaptive technology in Nasarawa zonal education board of Kano state.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Akintayo et al. (2024) conducted a systematic review to evaluate the impact of educational technology on learning outcome in the higher education sector. The researchers employed a comprehensive search strategy across multiple databases including peer reviewed journals and conference proceedings. Rigorous screening process, quality assessment and data extraction were used as methodology. The review includes a total of 47 studies which were analysed to identify patterns, themes and gaps in current literature. Key findings suggest that educational technology and learning processes can enhance student engagement, improve knowledge retention and foster higher order thinking skills. Furthermore, Anihenya and Agah (2021) studied the impact of technology integration to student's engagement and achievement in English and Mathematics in Mubi South local government area of Adamawa state. The study adopted survey research design. 250 SSII students were randomly selected from 4 schools. Mathematics/ English Engagement and Achievement Questionnaire (MEEAQ) was used to collect data. Mean, standard deviation and t-test were used as methods of data analysis. The study found that students from highly technology integrated schools had high level of academic engagement significantly than those from less technology integrated schools. Also, students from highly technology integration schools have high level of academic achievement than those from less technology integration school. The study concluded that technology integration is highly important for student engagement and achievement in schools. Moreover, Kumar (2024) examine the impact of technology on student's engagement and learning outcomes. Simple random sampling was used to select 100 students from various universities. Data was analysed using descriptive statistics such as

frequencies and percentages, and analysis of variables. The researcher found out that the majority of students reported using technology every day for their education indicating a high level of reliance on digital tools and resources. Also, a significant portion of students agreed or strongly agreed that technology heightened their involvement in learning. The study concluded that technology holds great potential to enhance student engagement and learning outcomes. Okocha et al. (2022) conducted research on effects of technologies on academic performance of Nigerian adolescents. The study adopted a survey research design. 120 adolescents were randomly selected and questionnaire was administered. Data was analysed using frequencies, simple percentage and standard deviation. The study found out that the use of digital technology has no negative effects on academic performance of students in Jos South local government area. Also, adolescents use digital technologies to disseminate knowledge to classmates. The study concludes that addiction and exposure to digital technology does have negative effects on them. Also, Katyara et al. (2022) studied the impact of technology on student's engagement in different dimensions: Cognitive, behavioural, reflective and social engagement at Iqra University, Karachi. The study was quantitative research approach with non-probability convenience sampling method and a sample size 400 undergraduate students. An adopted questionnaire was used from earlier studies with little modification. The findings reveals that there is positive and significant impact of technology on student's engagement and learning at undergraduate level. Also, technology has positive influence on behavioural, social, cognitive and reflective engagement among the students. The study recommended that proper work and focus should be given on training on technology use and overcome its related hurdles. Carstens et al. (2021) analyse the effects of technology on student learning. The researchers utilized a mixed method approach to understanding how the integration of technology affected students learning. A survey was developed and administered through Qualtrics to collect data. The survey was sent to K-12 educators at a local district in central Illinois. Participation was voluntary. The data was analysed using descriptive statistics such as mean, standard deviation and percentages. Qualitative data was analysed and organised into

emerging themes. The findings shows that there are many positive and negative aspects of technology use in classroom. Teachers felt that student motivation and engagement were higher with the use of technology in classroom. Also, more training for teachers and students are necessary to better implement technology in the classroom. More so, Attri (2024) examines the impact of technology on student engagement and learning outcomes in K-12 education through mixed methods approach the study combines quantitative data from standardized test scores and attendance records with qualitative insights from teacher and student's interviews. The findings indicates that technology when effectively implemented, enhances student engagement by providing interactive and personalized learning experiences. The researcher also emphasizes the importance of addressing implementation barriers to ensure equitable access and benefits for all. Wang (2024) studies the impact of modern technology on student learning outcomes. The research employed a secondary data analysis approach using the case study analysis of existing literature and data. The findings shows that technology can substantially augments student's cognitive skills by providing access to various resources and interactive platforms that support learning. From teacher's viewpoints, technology allows for more personalized learning experiences while diversifying teaching methods but its success requires adequate teacher training and support, parent's involvement for optimal use. The researcher recommends equitable access to technology for all students and internet connectivity irrespective of socio-economic backgrounds. Bhat (2023) examines the impact of technology integration on students learning outcomes. The study was a comparative study that examines the effects of technology integration on student learning outcomes by analysing existing literature, empirical data and case studies. Also, the study selected a sample of educational institutions that have embraced technology and comparing their learning outcomes with institutions that predominantly employ traditional methods. Student's performance indicators such as test scores, critical thinking skills and retention rates are analysed to gauge the impact of technology integration. Through an exploration of technology's various advantages, it becomes evident that technology has the capacity to revolutionize the

way students learn, engage and excel in their educational journeys. Lastly, Njoku et al. (2024) investigated the impact of technology integration in enhancing learning outcomes on childhood and primary education in Nigeria. The study was carried out in Hill Crest preparatory and primary school, Nsukka. A descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study with a population of 225 caregivers. The caregivers were selected without sampling due to the manageable population size. A structured questionnaire was developed by the researchers titled: Technology Integration in enhancing Learning Outcomes on Childhood and Primary Education Questionnaire (TILOCPQ). Cronbach alpha reliability coefficient was used to determine the instruments with a reliability coefficient of 0.84 mean and standard deviation were used as statistical measures to examine the research questions.

METHODOLOGY

Experimental research design known as Randomized Control Trial (RCT) was adopted for the study. Simkus (2024) defined Randomized Control Trial (RCT) as a type of study design that involves randomly assigning participants to either an experimental or a control group. The study was be conducted in schools under Nassarawa zonal education board. Nassarawa zonal education board consist of schools from two local government areas of Kano state, Nassarawa and Fagge. Nassarawa is located in the central part of kano with Hausa/Fulani as the predominant ethnic group. While Fagge is located at the north-western part of kano with different ethnic groups. There are 38 public schools under Nassarawa zonal education board. 22 schools located in Nassarawa local government and 16 in Fagge local government area with a total of 9864 students. Using research adviser 2006 the sample size will be 370 SS 2 students from 15 schools. Cluster random sampling was used to select the schools. Schools were grouped into clusters so that every area of the two selected local governments was covered in the research. 10 schools were selected from Nassarawa and 5 schools from Fagge local government area. Stratified random sampling was used to select 370 SS 2 students from the selected schools. Stratified random sampling was used so that boys and girls have equal chance of selection. Students were randomly

assigned to experimental or control group. 185 students comprising of both boys and girls were assigned to both the experimental and control groups. The experimental group received technological intervention such as on-line classes, personalized learning materials based on the needs of the students, one on one video calls and personal chats with the students on their economics lessons while the control group did not receive any form of technology intervention other than the conventional classroom lessons. Test and re-test were conducted on both the experimental and control groups and result from their terminal examination was analysed using t-tests.

Data analysis

Data collected was the result of terminal examination of 370 ss 2 students from 15 senior secondary school in Nassarawa zonal education board of kano state. 185 students were both assigned to the experimental and control group. 70% of the students were aged between 17 to 18 years of age and 30% were aged between 15

to 16 years. The consent of the selected schools, students and their guardians were gained before the commencement of the research. The data was analyzed using t-test. The results are discussed under each hypothesis.

H₀₁: There is no significant difference in the understanding and retention of complex concepts of SS 2 students that use digital resources and multimedia materials and those SS 2 students who do not use digital resources and multimedia materials in Nassarawa zonal education board of Kano state. To test the above hypothesis the mean of learning outcomes and student engagement of students that use digital resources and multimedia materials and those students who does not use digital resources and multimedia materials was used to conduct a test of differences. The coefficient of the differences was determined using independent sample t-test at 5% level of significance as presented in table 1 below;

t-Test: Two-Sample Assuming Unequal Variances

Table 1; Difference between students that use digital resources and multimedia materials and those who do not.

	Control	Experimental
Mean	40.27837838	62.52432432
Variance	64.13268214	120.0741334
Observations	185	185
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0	
df	337	
t Stat	-22.29378941	
P(T<=t) one-tail	1.36875E-68	
t Critical one-tail	1.649387728	
P(T<=t) two-tail	2.73751E-68	
t Critical two-tail	1.967028285	

The descriptive statistics and a test of difference using the independent sample t-test obtained as shown in Table 1, indicates that students who use digital resources and multimedia materials mean of learning outcomes and student engagement is M=62.52 and that of those who do not use digital resources and multimedia materials is M=40.27. Also, the variance between those students that use digital resources and multimedia materials are 120.07 and 64.13 respectively, df =337, p two tail is 0.000027, $\alpha=0.05$. the result of the analysis revealed a significant difference in mean of learning outcomes and student engagement of those students who use digital

resources and multimedia materials than those who do not use digital resources and multimedia material. The null hypothesis which says that, there is no significant difference in understanding and retention of complex concept of those SS 2 students who use digital resources and multimedia materials and those SS 2 students who do not use digital resources and multimedia materials is rejected since $0.000027 \leq 0.05$. This implies that there is a significant difference in the understanding and retention of complex concepts of SS2 students who use digital resources and multimedia resources and those SS 2 students

who do not use digital resources and multimedia materials.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference on the interest and engagement of SS 2 students that use personalized learning pathways and adaptive technology and those SS 2 students who do not use personalized learning pathways and adaptive technology in Nasarawa zonal education board of Kano state. To test the above hypothesis the mean of learning outcomes and student

engagement of students that use personalized learning pathways and adaptive technology and those students who does not use personalized learning styles and adaptive technology was used to conduct a test of differences. The coefficient of the differences was determined using independent sample t-test at 5% level of significance as presented in table 2 below;

t-Test: Two-Sample Assuming Unequal Variances

Table 2; Difference between those students that use personalized learning pathways and adaptive technology and those who do not.

	Control	Experimental
Mean	39.28918919	62.51621622
Variance	61.87107814	117.551366
Observations	185	185
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0	
df	336	
t Stat	-23.58528373	
P(T<=t) one-tail	1.51786E-73	
t Critical one-tail	1.64940126	
P(T<=t) two-tail	3.03572E-73	
t Critical two-tail	1.967049384	

The descriptive statistics and a test of difference using the independent sample t-test obtained as shown in Table 2, indicates that students who use personalized learning pathways and adaptive technology mean of learning outcomes and student engagement is M=62.51 and that of those who do not use personalized learning pathways and adaptive technology is M=39.28. Also, the variance between those students that use personalized learning pathways and adaptive technology are 117.35 and 61.87 respectively, df =336, p two tail is 0.000030, $\alpha=0.05$. The result of the analysis revealed a significant difference in mean of learning outcomes and student engagement of those students who use personalized learning pathways and adaptive technology than those who do not use personalized learning styles and adaptive technology. The null hypothesis which says that, there is no significant difference on the interest and engagement of those SS 2 students who use personalized learning pathways and adaptive technology and those SS 2 students who do not use personalized learning pathways and adaptive technology is rejected since $0.000030 \leq 0.05$. This implies that there is significant difference on the interest and engagement of those SS 2 students who

use personalized learning pathways and adaptive technology and those SS 2 students who do not use personalized learning pathways and adaptive technology.

SUMMARY OF FINDINGS

Based on the research the following are the findings of the study:

1. The researchers found out that students who attended online classes, had soft copies of their economics notes performed significantly better in their terminal examination than those who did not attend such classes. Thus, the learning outcomes and student engagement of those students who attended the online classes was significantly higher than those who did not attend the online classes.
2. The researchers found out that students who had personal chats, personalized learning materials and one on one chats and video calls showed a higher level of interest and engagement than those students who did not have such personalized learning pathways. Therefore, the students that used personalized learning pathways and adaptive

technology performed significantly better than those students who did use personalized learning pathways and adaptive technology.

CONCLUSION

Based in the findings of the study, SS 2 students who used digital resources and multimedia materials performed significantly better than those SS 2 students who did not use digital resources and multimedia materials. It was concluded that digital resources and multimedia materials have a significant impact on learning outcomes and student engagement of SS 2 students of Nassarawa zonal education board of Kano state. Also, the SS 2 students who used personalized learning pathways and adaptive technology showed a significantly higher level of interest and engagement than those who did use personalized learning pathways and adaptive technology. Thus, it was concluded that personalized learning pathways and adaptive technology have a significant impact on learning outcomes and student engagement of SS 2 students of Nassarawa zonal education board of Kano state. Therefore, the two hypotheses were rejected based on the statistical data. It can be concluded that since the use of digital resources, multimedia materials, personalized learning pathways and adaptive technology have a significant impact on learning outcomes and student engagement. Thus, the researchers concluded that technology integration has significant on learning outcomes and student engagement of SS 2 students of Nassarawa zonal education board.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings and conclusion of the study the following recommendations were made:

1. Kano state ministry of education should organize trainings, seminars and works for senior secondary teachers on how to utilize the integration of technology for better learning outcomes and student engagement.
2. Kano state ministry of education should encourage the integration of technology to public secondary schools so as to have better learning outcomes and student engagement.
3. Parents and guardian should realize the importance of technology integration in

determining students learning outcomes and engagement.

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HOW TO CITE: Saudat Bello Adamu*, Nuradeen Abdullahi Yusuf, Fatima Ahmad, Impact of Technology on Learning Outcomes and Student Engagement of SS 2 Students in Nassarawa Zonal Education Board of Kano State, *Int. J. Sci. R. Tech.*, 2025, 2 (11), 111-118. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17530703>